

FELACS: Federated Learning with Adaptive Client Selection for IoT DDoS Attack Detection

Mulualem Bitew Anley[✉], Pasquale Coscia[✉], Angelo Genovese^{✉*},
Vincenzo Piuri[✉]

Department of Computer Science, Università degli Studi di Milano, Italy

Abstract

Distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks pose a significant threat to network security by overwhelming systems with malicious traffic, leading to service disruptions and potential data breaches. The traditional centralized machine learning (ML) methods for detecting DDoS attacks in Internet of Things (IoT) environments raise privacy and security concerns due to their collection and distribution of data to a central entity that may not be trusted to perform model training. Federated learning (FL) offers a privacy-preserving solution that enables distributed collaboration by training a model only on local clients, without data exchanges, where the central entity only performs global model aggregation. However, the current practice of random client selection, combined with the statistical heterogeneity of client data and the device heterogeneity encountered in IoT environments, requires many training rounds to reach optimal accuracy, increasing the imposed computational overhead. To address these challenges, we propose a multiobjective optimization-based FL with adaptive client selection (FELACS) approach that maximizes client importance scores while satisfying resource, performance, and data diversity constraints. Experiments are carried out on the CIC-IDS2018, CIC-DDoS2019, BoT-IoT, and CIC-IoT2023 datasets, demonstrating that FELACS improves upon the accuracy of the existing approaches while exhibiting increased convergence speed when training a model in an FL scenario, hence reducing the number of communication rounds required to achieve the target accuracy, making it highly effective for performing IoT-based DDoS attack detection in FL scenarios.

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: mulualem.anley@unimi.it (Mulualem Bitew Anley[✉]),
pasquale.coscia@unimi.it (Pasquale Coscia[✉]), angelo.genovese@unimi.it
(Angelo Genovese[✉]), vincenzo.piuri@unimi.it (Vincenzo Piuri[✉])

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1. Introduction

Internet of Things (IoT) devices range from personalized health systems and home appliances to smart cities, playing a crucial role in everyday activities while frequently managing sensitive personal data. Safeguarding the privacy and security of these devices thus remains a critical challenge, with distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks currently being among the major threats encountered in IoT environments (Pakmehr et al., 2024). Centralized intrusion detection systems (IDSs) based on machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) have been extensively researched for detecting these attacks (Gümüşbaş et al., 2021; Aktar and Nur, 2023). However, centralized DL-based IDSs are often inadequate for scaling and adapting to the distributed nature and privacy requirements of IoT environments (Fotse et al., 2024). Federated learning (FL) has since been considered for detecting cybersecurity threats, enabling collaborative data analyses without requiring the transfer of private data between organizations (McMahan et al., 2017; Nguyen et al., 2025; Mazid et al., 2025; Rahmati, 2025; Olanrewaju-George and Pranggono, 2025).

FL begins with the central server distributing an initial model to a subset of the selected clients. The client selection process plays a crucial role, as it directly influences both the performance and convergence rate of the global model. In IoT-based environments, additional client selection challenges are posed by the high degree of device heterogeneity. In fact, IoT devices produce datasets that can vary significantly in their sizes and feature spaces, resulting in devices that possess many samples for certain types of DDoS attacks while having minimal data for others. Such heterogeneity necessitates distinct representations of data across different organizations, which is a requirement that existing FL frameworks might not fulfill without adaptations for addressing diverse feature spaces and device capabilities. Furthermore, DDoS attacks executed in IoT environments exhibit different characteristics across various devices, further complicating the analysis due to their statistical heterogeneity (Li et al., 2024; Anley et al., 2025).

The client selection approaches described in the literature often do not explicitly account for the relevance and importance of the data held by each client since the selection of clients traditionally occurs via either a random or semirandom approach (McMahan et al., 2017; Nishio and Yonetani, 2019; Wu et al., 2023).

34 In fact, such approaches can lead to the selection of less valuable data, resulting
35 in suboptimal model performance in the presence of heterogeneous clients (Fu
36 et al., 2023). While more recent works have proposed algorithms that consider
37 criteria such as accuracy, CPU capacity, memory, energy levels, and response
38 times (Zhao et al., 2018; Li et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2020; AbdulRahman et al.,
39 2020; Seo et al., 2022; Maciel et al., 2023; Sun et al., 2024; Nguyen et al., 2025;
40 Mazid et al., 2025), they do not dynamically adapt to changing data quality and
41 device performance conditions throughout the training rounds of FL, resulting in
42 possible model training inefficiencies and slower convergence speeds. In fact,
43 most of the existing methods focus on either data importance or computational
44 efficiency but rarely combine these factors into a unified approach. Furthermore,
45 most current client selection strategies assume static client participation, whereas
46 real-world IoT environments are characterized by high client mobility rates and
47 frequent connectivity disruptions (Zhang et al., 2024).

48 In this paper, we propose federated learning with adaptive client selection
49 (FELACS): a novel and adaptive framework that is designed to optimize the client
50 participation level for performing DDoS detection in IoT environments.¹ FELACS
51 introduces a multicriteria, multiobjective optimization-based selection strategy
52 that integrates client resource constraints, data diversity, relevance, and system
53 efficiency for each training round. This comprehensive framework evaluates key
54 factors such as data entropy, statistical variance, computational efficiency, energy
55 consumption, and communication latency. By leveraging these diverse criteria,
56 FELACS ensures the adaptive selection of high-impact clients in each round, facil-
57 itating robust model updates, a faster convergence speed, and improved detection
58 accuracy. Moreover, our proposed approach addresses the unique challenges posed
59 by DDoS attack detection in IoT-based FL scenarios, where timely and accurate
60 client selection is critical for achieving effective real-time threat detection. In this
61 context, FELACS prioritizes clients with higher-level representations of attack-
62 related data, thus improving the relevance and quality of the updates derived from
63 participating clients. This strategy accelerates the attack detection procedure,
64 reduces the required convergence time, and enhances the responsiveness of the
65 system. By shifting from resource-centric selection to a data-driven and adaptive
66 approach, FELACS establishes a new paradigm for selecting clients in FL settings.

67 The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides an

¹The source code will be made available upon the acceptance of this work at <https://github.com/mulerkal/FELACS>.

68 overview of the related works in the field of FL for IoT security, IoT IDSs, and
69 DDoS attack detection, with a focus on client selection strategies. Section 3
70 describes the system model, problem formulation, and FL learning process of
71 the developed method. Section 4 outlines the methodology and algorithm of our
72 proposed approach, including the experimental design, dataset details, and model
73 architecture. Section 5 presents the results of our proposed methodology and a
74 corresponding performance analysis. Finally, Section 6 summarizes this work and
75 concludes the paper.

76 **2. Related Works**

77 *FL in IoT Security and Intrusion Detection Scenarios.* Unlike centralized ML-
78 based DDoS attack detection (Agostinello et al., 2023; Anley et al., 2024), which
79 poses challenges such as privacy risks, high latency, and potential network con-
80 gestion (Feng et al., 2021), an FL-based IDS provides a decentralized alternative
81 in which the model training process is distributed across different IoT devices,
82 thereby minimizing the data transfer requirements and reducing privacy concerns
83 (Li et al., 2020a; Kairouz et al., 2021; Lim et al., 2020). FL-based IDSs can
84 achieve comparable accuracy to that of centralized methods while preserving data
85 privacy (Roy et al., 2023) and simultaneously addressing the distributed nature of
86 IoT networks, where devices may have varying computational capabilities and data
87 characteristics (Ruzafa-Alcázar et al., 2021). In fact, several works have explicitly
88 considered FL tasks with nonindependent and identically distributed (non-IID)
89 data, which are caused by IoT devices often having skewed data distributions, with
90 certain devices collecting extensive data on specific attack types while possess-
91 ing limited data on other types (Ma et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2018). Because of
92 the presence of non-IID data, traditional aggregation techniques such as feder-
93 ated averaging (FedAvg), which consider the contributions of each client equally
94 (McMahan et al., 2017), struggle to manage the high degree of data heterogeneity
95 encountered in real-world scenarios. This heterogeneity can hinder the overall
96 performance and convergence speed of the global model.

97 *Client Selection in FL.* In FL, the learning process is distributed across multiple
98 clients, which collaboratively train a global model by sharing their locally com-
99 puted updates instead of raw data. Efficient client selection mechanisms ensure
100 an effective model training procedure while optimizing the incurred communica-
101 tion costs and preserving the diversity of the given data (McMahan et al., 2017;
102 Bonawitz et al., 2019). Studies on the selection of clients in FL tasks have

103 explored various strategies that consider client availability, data quality, computa-
104 tional capacity, and model performance contributions (Wang et al., 2020; Nishio
105 and Yonetani, 2019).

106 The simplest way to perform client selection, other than a random-based ap-
107 proach (McMahan et al., 2017; Nishio and Yonetani, 2019; Wu et al., 2023; Ginan-
108 jar et al., 2025), consists of considering only the contributions of clients to reducing
109 the loss function of the global model. For example, the approaches described in
110 (Wang et al., 2020; Seo et al., 2022) prioritize clients with higher expected model
111 accuracy contributions, improving their convergence speeds relative to that of ran-
112 dom client selection, particularly in heterogeneous data environments where some
113 clients possess more informative or diverse data than others do. However, these
114 approaches overlook the computational capacities of clients and the associated
115 communication costs, potentially leading to increased latency and inefficiencies
116 in resource-constrained IoT networks. To improve this model, more recently de-
117 veloped approaches also consider resources and device capabilities (Maciel et al.,
118 2023). For example, the federated proximal (FedProx) approach was designed to
119 handle systems with varying computational resources by enabling partial client
120 participation during training, thus reducing the update variability caused by het-
121 erogeneous datasets (Li et al., 2020b). However, FedProx does not account for
122 the diversity and significance of client data during the selection process. Exten-
123 sions to resource-aware client selection are represented by the FedCS (Nishio and
124 Yonetani, 2019) and FedMCCS (AbdulRahman et al., 2020) methods, which se-
125 lect clients on the basis of availability, computational power, and communication
126 bandwidth; dynamically adjust the number of selected clients; and allocate more
127 resources to those with higher capabilities. However, these approaches assume that
128 clients are willing to fully disclose their resource states, which may not be feasible
129 because of privacy concerns or the risk of unreliable self-reporting in real-world
130 IoT environments.

131 Recent advances have also explored client selection approaches based on data
132 diversity to increase the generalizability of FL models. In the method described
133 in (Zhao et al., 2018), the issue of data heterogeneity is addressed through a data-
134 sharing mechanism, where a small amount of globally shared data is used to align
135 the learning objectives of different clients. This method improves the convergence
136 of the global model but undermines the fundamental privacy-preserving principle
137 of FL, as even minimal data sharing could expose sensitive information. To
138 counteract this issue, the method proposed in (Li et al., 2021) considers a diversity-
139 aware client selection scheme that encourages participation from clients with
140 diverse data distributions, thereby enhancing the robustness of the model without

141 requiring data sharing. While promising, this approach relies heavily on the
142 accurate estimation of data diversity, which may not always be feasible, especially
143 in environments with highly dynamic IoT network data distributions.

144 To account for both data- and resource-based device client characteristics,
145 multicriteria client selection schemes have been proposed for ensuring reliable
146 and secure participation in FL. As an example, (Tahir et al., 2025) proposed Se-
147 cureFedPROM, a framework that integrates security, performance, and system
148 efficiency metrics into a weighted multiarmed bandit (MAB) model for dynami-
149 cally ranking clients. The method introduced in (Ami et al., 2025) further leverages
150 an MAB-based scheduler to learn the computational and network profiles of clients
151 over time, thereby minimizing the training latency induced per round.

152 3. System Model and Problem Formulation

153 In this section, we introduce FELACS, an adaptive client selection algorithm
154 that is designed to enhance the FL-based DDoS detection process in IoT environ-
155 nments. We begin by describing the system model and then formalize the FELACS
156 problem. Table 1 summarizes the notations and symbols used in the equations
157 presented in this work.

158 3.1. System Model

159 The proposed FELACS framework operates within an FL environment to detect
160 DDoS attacks in IoT networks. The system consists of a central server and a set of
161 distributed clients \mathcal{N} , where each client $k \in \mathcal{N}$ owns a local dataset \mathcal{D}_k consisting
162 of traffic from its private network. The central server maintains a global model
163 \mathbf{w}_t , which is a classifier of the normal and DDoS traffic encountered in iteration t .
164 In each iteration t , each client downloads the model, trains it on its local data, and
165 transmits updates back to the server.

166 After an initialization phase, the training process is divided into communication
167 rounds, each of which consists of three phases: *i*) client selection, *ii*) client
168 updating, and *iii*) model aggregation. The process then follows the subsequent
169 steps until the maximum number of communication rounds is reached or until the
170 convergence criteria are satisfied.

171 *Step 1: Client Selection.* In each round t , the server assesses the capabilities
172 of each device (i.e., its network latency, power consumption, and computational
173 resources) and uses the proposed FELACS algorithm to select a subset of clients
174 $S_t \subseteq \mathcal{N}$ from the total pool of clients \mathcal{N} , with $|\mathcal{N}| = K$ total clients. This step is
175 explained in detail in Section 3.2.

Table 1: Notations and descriptions used throughout the paper.

Symbol	Description
\mathcal{N}	Set of all clients participating in FL.
k	Client index, where $k \in \mathcal{N}$.
\mathcal{D}_k	Local dataset held by client k .
t	Communication round index.
$S_t \subseteq \mathcal{N}$	Subset of clients selected in round t .
\mathbf{w}_t	Global model in round t .
\mathbf{w}_k^t	Updated local model parameters after client k trains on \mathcal{D}_k in round t .
$\nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_t)$	Gradient of the loss function F_k of client k evaluated at \mathbf{w}_t .
η	Learning rate for local stochastic gradient descent (SGD) updates.
K	Upper bound imposed on the number of clients selected per round.
R_{\max}	Total resource budget available for client selection.
L_{\max}	Maximum allowable communication latency per client.
H_{\min}	Minimum Shannon entropy required for the data of a client to qualify.
$\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$	Hyperparameters for weighting the components of the importance score.
I_i	Importance score of client i , defined as $I_i = \alpha H(\mathcal{D}_i) + \beta V(\mathcal{D}_i) - \gamma P_i - \delta L_i$.
E	Number of local training epochs executed on each selected client per round.
y_i^c	One-hot encoded true label of sample i for class c .
$f(x_i; \mathbf{w}_t)_c$	Predicted probability of class c for input x_i under model \mathbf{w}_t .
C	Total number of classes involved in the classification task.
n_k	Number of data points contained in \mathcal{D}_k .
$n \sum_{k \in S_t} n_k$	Total number of samples across all selected clients in round t .
R_i	Resource consumption (e.g., CPU cycles) of client i .
P_i	Power consumption of client i .
L_i	Network latency of client i .
u_i	Utility score of client i .
$H(\mathcal{D}_i)$	Shannon entropy of the data distribution at client i .
$V(\mathcal{D}_i)$	Variance of the data distribution of client i .
T_{dl}	$\frac{\text{model size}}{\text{downlink bandwidth}} + \text{latency}$.
$T_{\text{comp}}^{(i)}$	$E \cdot \frac{N_i}{\text{batch size}} \cdot t_{\text{batch}}^{(i)}$.
$T_{\text{ul}}^{(i)}$	$\frac{\text{update size}}{\text{uplink bandwidth}} + \text{latency}$.
T_{agg}	Aggregation time per round.

176 *Step 2: Client Updating.* The selected clients download the current global model
 177 \mathbf{w}_t . Each client $k \in S_t$ trains the model on its local dataset \mathcal{D}_k for E epochs
 178 and computes the updated local model parameters \mathbf{w}_t^k . The update process is as
 179 follows:

$$\mathbf{w}_t^k = \mathbf{w}_t - \eta \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_t) , \quad (1)$$

180 where η is the learning rate and $\nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_t)$ represents the gradient of the local
 181 loss function $F_k(\mathbf{w}_t)$, which quantifies the error induced by the model on the
 182 local dataset of the client \mathcal{D}_k . We define the local loss function $F_k(\mathbf{w}_t)$ as the
 183 cross-entropy loss:

$$F_k(\mathbf{w}_t) = -\frac{1}{|\mathcal{D}_k|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{D}_k} \sum_{c=1}^C y_i^c \log f(x_i; \mathbf{w}_t)^c , \quad (2)$$

184 where y_i^c is the one-hot encoded label produced for class c , $f(x_i; \mathbf{w}_t)^c$ is the
 185 predicted probability for class c , and C is the total number of classes.

186 *Step 3: Model Aggregation.* The server aggregates the local updates obtained
 187 from the selected clients to update the global model. The server-side steps involve
 188 collecting updates \mathbf{w}_t^k from each selected client $k \in S_t$ and aggregating the updates
 189 to form a new global model, thereby obtaining \mathbf{w}_{t+1} :

$$\mathbf{w}_{t+1} = \sum_{k \in S_t} \frac{n_k}{n} \mathbf{w}_t^k , \quad (3)$$

190 where n_k is the number of data points for client k and $n = \sum_{k \in S_t} n_k$. By
 191 aggregating these updates from the selected clients, the global model optimizes
 192 the overall objective:

$$F(\mathbf{w}_t) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K F_k(\mathbf{w}_t) , \quad (4)$$

193 where K is the total number of clients. The system model is detailed in Algo-
 194 rithm 1.

195 3.2. FELACS Problem Formulation

196 The objective of FELACS is to increase the convergence rate and maximize the
 197 DDoS attack detection accuracy of the developed model by selecting an optimal
 198 subset S_t of clients during each communication round t . The client selection
 199 process is framed as an optimization problem aimed at maximizing the achieved

Algorithm 1: FELACS System Model

Input: Client pool \mathcal{N} , total number of rounds T , maximum number of clients per round K , number of local epochs E , learning rate η .

Output: Global model \mathbf{w}_t .

Initialization.

$\mathbf{w}_0 \leftarrow$ initial model parameters

for $t \leftarrow 0$ **to** $T - 1$ **do**

Step 1: Client Selection.

$S_t \leftarrow \text{SELECTCLIENTS}(\mathcal{N}, K)$ (see Algorithm 2)

Step 2: Client Updating.

foreach $k \in S_t$ **in parallel do**

Client k downloads \mathbf{w}_t and trains for E epochs on \mathcal{D}_k

$\mathbf{w}_t^k \leftarrow \mathbf{w}_t - \eta \nabla F_k(\mathbf{w}_t)$

Step 3: Model Aggregation.

$n_k =$ number of data points for client k

$\mathbf{w}_{t+1} = \sum_{k \in S_t} \frac{n_k}{\sum_{j \in S_t} n_j} \mathbf{w}_t^k$

200 detection accuracy while respecting the imposed computational and communica-
201 tion constraints, and it is guided by the total importance score I_i of the selected
202 clients. The **importance score** for client i is defined as follows:

$$I_i = \alpha H(\mathcal{D}_i) + \beta V(\mathcal{D}_i) - \gamma P_i - \delta L_i, \quad (5)$$

203 where $H(\mathcal{D}_i)$ is the Shannon entropy of the data of client i , representing the
204 diversity of the data; $V(\mathcal{D}_i)$ is the variance of the local data of client i , which reflects
205 the statistical heterogeneity of the data distribution of this client; P_i represents the
206 power consumption of client i ; L_i represents the network latency of client i ; and
207 $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta$ are hyperparameters for controlling the relative influence of each factor
208 (see also Table 1).

209 We model the process of selecting an optimal subset of clients S_t in each
210 round t as a multiobjective optimization problem, specifically a multidimensional
211 knapsack problem (MDKP). In this formulation, each candidate device i is char-
212 acterized by a cost vector (resource, power, latency) and a utility that reflects its
213 data relevance and expected contribution to the global model. The objective is to
214 maximize the total utility under the constraint that the sum of the costs does not

215 exceed the available budget.

216 We formulate the optimization problem to maximize the total importance score
 217 of the selected clients while respecting the imposed resource, power, latency, data
 218 diversity, and participation constraints (Equation 6):

$$\operatorname{argmax}_{S_t} \sum_{i \in S_t} (I_i) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{subject to: } \sum_{i \in S_t} R_i \leq R_{\max}, \quad (7)$$

$$\sum_{i \in S_t} P_i \leq P_{\max}, \quad (8)$$

$$L_i \leq L_{\max}, \quad \forall i \in S_t, \quad (9)$$

$$H(\mathcal{D}_i) \geq H_{\min}, \quad \forall i \in S_t, \quad (10)$$

$$|S_t| \leq K. \quad (11)$$

219 The optimization problem must satisfy the following constraints.

- 220 1. *Client resource constraints.* The total resource usage $\sum_{i \in S_t} R_i$ of the se-
 221 lected clients must not exceed the available resource budget R_{\max} . This
 222 constraint helps manage the computational and communication limitations
 223 of IoT devices, ensuring an efficient client selection process without over-
 224 burdening the system (Equation 7).
- 225 2. *Power constraint.* The total power consumption level $\sum_{i \in S_t} P_i$ for the
 226 selected clients should be bounded by P_{\max} to ensure that battery-powered
 227 devices retain sufficient energy for completing their training procedures
 228 (Equation 8).
- 229 3. *Latency constraints.* The latency L_i of each selected client should be
 230 bounded by L_{\max} to ensure timely model updates (Equation 9).
- 231 4. *Data diversity constraints.* To ensure diversity, clients with high data redun-
 232 dancy levels are excluded. The entropy of the data of the selected clients
 233 $H(\mathcal{D}_i)$ must exceed a threshold H_{\min} (Equation 10).
- 234 5. *Client selection constraints.* The number of selected clients $|S_t|$ should not
 235 exceed a predefined limit K (Equation 11).

236 The defined multidimensional client selection problem is a nondeterministic
 237 polynomial-time (NP)-hard problem, so we adopt a fast three-step greedy heuristic
 238 approach. *i)* First, we discard any client i for which $L_i > L_{\max}$ or $H(\mathcal{D}_i) < H_{\min}$,

239 thereby enforcing the latency and diversity constraints up front. For each remaining
240 client, we compute the importance-per-resource ratio ρ_i as shown below:

$$\rho_i = \frac{I_i}{R_i}, \quad (12)$$

241 which quantifies the marginal benefit of selecting i relative to its cost. The
242 importance-per-resource ratio balances its potential benefit against its resource
243 consumption level. *ii)* Then, we sort the clients in descending order of ρ_i (an
244 $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ operation). *iii)* Finally, we traverse this list from the highest to the
245 lowest values of ρ_i and iteratively add clients to S_t until adding a further client
246 would violate a constraint ($\mathcal{O}(n)$ per pass). In this case, we apply an algorithm
247 to repair constraint violations by removing the violating client and looking for
248 the next-best client in the ρ_i rankings until we find a candidate whose addition
249 does not violate any constraint. Algorithm 2 details the proposed client selection
250 algorithm.

251 We adopt a three-step greedy heuristic for FELACS because it runs in $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$
252 time, uses only linear memory, and imposes negligible computation and communi-
253 cation overhead, which are critical properties for resource-constrained, intermittent-
254 ly connected IoT devices. Alternative approaches for solving the MDKP include
255 integer linear programming (ILP) solvers, LP relaxation with rounding (Anand
256 et al., 2017; Puchinger et al., 2010), population-based metaheuristics (Elfaki et al.,
257 2023), and multiobjective optimization frameworks tailored to FL (Hu et al., 2022).
258 While these approaches offer various optimality or approximation guarantees, they
259 typically exhibit exponential runtime growth, require careful parameter tuning, or
260 demand substantial communication and memory resources, leading to elevated
261 latency and energy consumption levels, which are untenable in intermittently con-
262 nected IoT networks.

263 4. Evaluation Methodology

264 4.1. Experimental Design

265 We use the Flower² FL framework for our simulations because of its versatility
266 and customization options that are tailored to the IoT and client-server configura-
267 tions (Beutel et al., 2020).

²<https://flower.ai>

Algorithm 2: FELACS Algorithm for Client Selection

Input: Client pool \mathcal{N} , maximum number of clients K , resource budget R_{\max} , latency L_{\max} , entropy threshold H_{\min} , weights $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta)$.

Output: Selected client subset S_t .

Step 1.

Compute importance score I_i .

foreach $i \in \mathcal{N}$ **do**

┌ $I_i \leftarrow \alpha H(\mathcal{D}_i) + \beta V(\mathcal{D}_i) - \gamma P_i - \delta L_i$

Compute importance-per-resource ratio ρ_i .

foreach $i \in \mathcal{N}$ **do**

┌ $\rho_i \leftarrow \frac{I_i}{R_i}$

Step 2: Sort clients.

Sort \mathcal{N} in descending order of ρ_i

Step 3.

Client selection under constraints.

$S_t \leftarrow \emptyset$

foreach i in sorted \mathcal{N} **do**

┌ **if** $|S_t| < K$ **and** $\sum_{j \in S_t} R_j + R_i \leq R_{\max}$ **and** $L_i \leq L_{\max}$ **and**

┌ $H(\mathcal{D}_i) \geq H_{\min}$ **then**

┌ $S_t \leftarrow S_t \cup \{i\}$

Repair constraint violations.

foreach $j \in S_t$ **if** $(L_j > L_{\max}$ **or** $H(\mathcal{D}_j) < H_{\min})$ **do**

┌ Find next-best $k \notin S_t$ with the highest I_k satisfying all constraints

┌ Replace j with k in S_t

return S_t

268 4.2. Datasets

269 We perform our experiments on widely applied benchmark IDS and DDoS
270 attack detection datasets. Specifically, we consider the CIC-IDS2018 (Sharafaldin
271 et al., 2018), CIC-DDoS2019 (Sharafaldin et al., 2019), BoT-IoT (Koroniotis et al.,
272 2019), and CIC-IoT2023 (Neto et al., 2023) datasets. These datasets enable both
273 binary and multiclass classification, as well as FL model training. Moreover, BoT-
274 IoT and CIC-IoT2023 describe realistic IoT traffic in modern networks. Table 2
275 lists the different datasets in terms of their classes and numbers of samples.

276 To simulate an FL scenario for a dataset that does not explicitly divide its data
277 into clients, in this paper, we distribute the preprocessed dataset among five clients

Table 2: Traffic types and their cardinality across four datasets.

CIC-IDS2018		CIC-DDoS2019		BoT-IoT		CIC-IoT2023	
Type	Card.	Type	Card.	Type	Card.	Type	Card.
Benign	1 603 315	TFTP	4 396 770	Benign	590 298	DDoS	5 338 243
LoIC-HTTP	143 746	UDP	2 510 574	DDoS	379 302	DoS	1 269 264
HOIC	49 677	NTP	1 112 902	Reconn	108 795	Mirai	413 754
Hulk	36 227	SSDP	891 220	Theft	31 746	Benign	172 642
SlowHTTPTest	10 308	SYN	687 524	Scan	9 164	Spoofing	76 807
GoldenEye	2 419	MSSQL	484 070	-	-	Recon	55 531
Slowloris	433	SNMP	114 179	-	-	Web	3 836
LOIC-UDP	154	DNS	113 252	-	-	BruteForce	1 988
-	-	BENIGN	99 154	-	-	-	-
-	-	LDAP	48 469	-	-	-	-
-	-	NetBIOS	31 052	-	-	-	-
-	-	Portmap	1 638	-	-	-	-
Total:	1 846 279	Total:	10 491 218	Total:	1 119 305	Total:	7 332 065

Table 3: Data distribution of the CIC-IDS2018 dataset among five clients after performing preprocessing to simulate non-IID data.

Traffic Type	IoT1	IoT2	IoT3	IoT4	IoT5
Benign	269 431	351 565	503 600	248 003	230 716
LOIC-HTTP	24 155	31 519	45 150	22 234	20 688
HOIC	8 347	10 891	15 602	7 683	7 154
Hulk	6 087	7 943	11 378	5 602	5 217
SlowHTTPTest	1 731	2 260	3 237	1 593	1 487
GoldenEye	406	529	759	373	352
Slowloris	71	94	135	66	67
LOIC-UDP	29	41	17	31	36
Total	310 230	404 804	579 865	285 555	265 687

278 using random sampling to simulate its non-IID nature. Table 3 shows an example
 279 of the data distribution for the CIC-IDS2018 dataset, where each client is assigned
 280 a varying number of samples from each class to simulate a realistic non-IID data
 281 distribution. The purpose of this setting is to evaluate the performance of our
 282 model in terms of handling heterogeneous data distributions, which are commonly
 283 encountered in IoT environments. In the following, we briefly describe the datasets
 284 and their main characteristics.

285 **CIC-IDS2018.** This dataset was specifically designed to simulate realistic network
 286 traffic³, and it includes various attack scenarios captured over five days, including

³<https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/ids-2018.html>

Table 4: Data distribution of the BoT-IoT dataset.

Traffic type	IoT1	IoT2	IoT3	IoT4	IoT5
Benign	295 649	148 000	73 000	36 500	37 149
DDoS	189 651	94 825	47 413	23 706	23 707
Reconn	54 395	27 197	13 599	6 800	6 804
Theft	15 873	7 937	3 968	1 984	1 984
Scan	4 582	2 291	1 145	572	574
Total	560 150	280 250	139 125	69 562	70 218

287 DoS, DDoS, brute force, and infiltration attacks. Each record contained in the
 288 dataset comprises 80 features extracted using CICFlowMeter, including details
 289 regarding time stamps, source and destination IPs, protocols, and packet lengths
 290 (Sharafaldin et al., 2018).

291 **CIC-DDoS2019.** This dataset, which was released by the Canadian Institute
 292 for Cybersecurity, offers a realistic benchmark for performing DDoS detection
 293 by combining benign background traffic synthesized via the B-Profile system to
 294 emulate 25 users across HTTP, HTTPS, FTP, SSH, and email, with a diverse mix
 295 of reflection and amplification attacks⁴. The training set includes 12 distinct attack
 296 variants, whereas the testing set covers 7 variants. All traffic was captured as raw
 297 PCAPs per host and processed with CICFlowMeter to extract over 80 flow-based
 298 features, yielding tens of millions of labeled flows for both binary and multiclass
 299 DDoS research (Sharafaldin et al., 2019).

300 **BoT-IoT.** This dataset was collected at the University of New South Wales (UNSW)
 301 Canberra’s Cyber Range Lab and describes normal and malicious DDoS traffic
 302 in a realistic network environment⁵. The data were collected from IoT devices,
 303 including refrigerators, sound systems, thermostats, lights, and locks. These
 304 devices are represented as IoT1 through IoT5, as depicted in Table 4. Each
 305 device simulates different network environments and attack patterns, allowing
 306 for a comprehensive evaluation of the proposed approach in an FL scenario. This
 307 dataset covers various cyber threats, including DDoS, DoS, reconnaissance, service
 308 scan, and theft attacks (Koroniotis et al., 2019).

309 **CIC-IoT2023.** This dataset describes large-scale IoT attack data captured on a
 310 realistic testbed consisting of 105 heterogeneous devices, featuring 33 distinct

⁴<https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/ddos-2019.html>

⁵<https://research.unsw.edu.au/projects/bot-iot-dataset>

311 attack variants across seven categories (DDoS, DoS, reconnaissance, web exploit,
312 brute-force, spoofing, and Mirai botnet commands) against benign traffic⁶ (Neto
313 et al., 2023).

314 4.3. Data Distributions

315 For each of the considered datasets, we randomly allocate 80% of the records
316 to the training partition and reserve the remaining 20% of the data for centralized
317 testing. The training subsets are then distributed across K federated nodes to
318 approximate realistic IoT deployments. Each node holds a distinct slice of the data
319 that reflects its local traffic conditions. Moreover, the held-out 20% remains the
320 same across all the experiments to ensure a fair performance comparison for the
321 global model.

322 To induce non-IID heterogeneity, we employ Dirichlet sampling $\text{Dir}(\alpha)$ over
323 the class labels, which is a commonly used technique in FL studies (Hsu et al.,
324 2019). Specifically, for each node k and each traffic class c (benign or one of the
325 attack types), we draw proportions $p_{k,c} \sim \text{Dir}(\alpha)$ and assign roughly $p_{k,c} \times N_{\text{train}}$
326 samples from class c to node k , where N_{train} is the total number of training records.
327 By varying α , we control the skewness, thus defining three levels of heterogeneity:
328 mild, moderate, and severe. With $\alpha = 10$, the class distributions across the nodes
329 remain close to IID (*mild heterogeneity*), $\alpha = 1$ produces a noticeable imbalance
330 between the benign and malicious traffic (*moderate heterogeneity*), and $\alpha = 0.1$
331 yields highly skewed partitions in which some nodes see almost exclusively benign
332 samples or almost exclusively attack samples (*severe heterogeneity*).

333 4.4. Model Architecture

334 The convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture used in our experiments
335 is specifically designed for detecting DDoS attacks in IoT environments. It uses two
336 Conv1D layers, each of which is followed by rectified linear unit (ReLU) activa-
337 tion and batch normalization functions, to enhance its feature stability. Maximum
338 pooling layers are interleaved to reduce the spatial dimensionality of the network,
339 and dropout layers are applied to mitigate overfitting. The output of the convolu-
340 tional blocks is then flattened and passed through a dense layer with 256 neurons,
341 culminating in a Softmax layer for multiclass classification (Table 5). This design
342 is chosen for its demonstrated ability to capture hierarchical patterns in network
343 traffic, which is critical for accurately distinguishing between benign and malicious
344 flows in IoT settings (Anley et al., 2024).

⁶<https://www.unb.ca/cic/datasets/iotdataset-2023.html>

Table 5: Proposed 1D-CNN architecture of the model.

Layer	Filters/Units	Output Shape	Activation	Parameters
Input window	–	(input)	–	0
Conv1D	64	(254, 64)	Sigmoid	256
MaxPool1D	–	(127, 64)	–	0
Dropout	–	(127, 64)	–	0
Conv1D	128	(125, 128)	ReLU	24 704
MaxPool1D	–	(62, 128)	–	0
Dropout	–	(62, 128)	–	0
Conv1D	256	(60, 256)	ReLU	98 560
MaxPool1D	–	(30, 256)	–	0
Dropout	–	(30, 256)	–	0
Flatten	–	(7 680)	–	0
Dense	256	(256)	ReLU	983 168
Dropout	–	(256)	–	0
Dense (output)	–	(output)	Softmax	256

345 For comparison purposes, we also consider Visual Geometry Group 16 (VGG16),
346 which is a 16-layer convolutional network composed of five convolutional blocks,
347 each comprising consecutive 3×3 convolutions followed by maximum pooling,
348 and three fully connected layers at the top. Its deeper architecture allows for a more
349 hierarchical feature extraction process than that performed by our CNN, exhibiting
350 high accuracy in DDoS attack detection scenarios (Anley et al., 2024; Agostinello
351 et al., 2023). In our evaluations, we integrate FELACS with both the shallow
352 CNN and VGG16, with the resulting models referred to as FELACS+CNN and
353 FELACS+VGG16, respectively, to assess how increased depth can influence the
354 convergence speed and classification accuracy of a model under heterogeneous
355 IoT traffic distributions.

356 During the model evaluation procedure, we apply an early stopping criterion
357 at the local client level to halt the training process when the performance plateaus.
358 In the FL framework, we vary the number of communication rounds to observe its
359 update dynamics, and the pool of participating clients for each round is determined
360 according to our FELACS-based selection strategy. The learning rate is carefully
361 tuned to balance the convergence and stability of the model, and a dropout rate
362 of 20% is enforced to enhance its robustness against noisy or incomplete IoT
363 data. For the loss computation, we use the binary cross-entropy loss to distinguish
364 between benign and DDoS traffic and employ the categorical cross-entropy loss
365 when classifying specific DDoS attack types.

366 **4.5. Evaluation Metrics**

367 To assess the performance of our FL models, we consider the following metrics:
 368 *i*) accuracy, which is defined as the proportion of correctly classified instances out
 369 of the total number of instances; *ii*) precision, which is defined as the ratio of true-
 370 positive predictions to the total number of predicted positives; *iii*) recall, which
 371 is expressed as the ratio of true-positive predictions to the total number of actual
 372 positives; *iv*) the F1 score, which is computed as the harmonic mean of precision
 373 and recall; and *v*) the training time, which is measured as the total time required
 374 to complete the training rounds, including the communication and computation
 375 times.

376 We define the total training time T_{total} as the sum of the per-round computation
 377 and communication latencies over all R federated rounds:

$$T_{\text{total}} = \sum_{r=1}^R \left[T_{\text{dl}} + \max_{i \in \mathcal{S}} \left(T_{\text{comp}}^{(i)} + T_{\text{ul}}^{(i)} \right) + T_{\text{agg}} \right]. \quad (13)$$

378 In each federated round, client i performs local computations on its own data in
 379 time $T_{\text{comp}}^{(i)} \left(E \times \frac{N_i}{\text{batch size}} \times t_{\text{batch}}^{(i)} \right)$. The server first incurs a download delay of
 380 T_{dl} when the global model is sent to clients (server(client)). After the local training
 381 process, client i uploads its update in time $T_{\text{ul}}^{(i)}$ (client(server)). Since the server
 382 waits for the slowest client, the combined communication and computation cost in
 383 that round is $\max_{i \in \mathcal{S}} \left(T_{\text{comp}}^{(i)} + T_{\text{ul}}^{(i)} \right) + T_{\text{dl}}$. Once all the updates arrive, the server
 384 aggregates them in time T_{agg} .

385 **5. Results and Discussion**

386 This section includes an evaluation of the proposed adaptive client selection
 387 approach for conducting FL to detect DDoS attacks within IoT environments. We
 388 first assess the performance of the model in client-side evaluations. Next, we
 389 conduct experiments within FL settings, comparing the results with those of the
 390 centralized model. We apply the proposed client selection algorithm and compare
 391 its performance with that of the state-of-the-art methods, analyzing the accuracies
 392 of the tested models under both IID and non-IID data settings. Finally, we evaluate
 393 the communication overhead, latency, sensitivity, and convergence time of the
 394 proposed model throughout the communication rounds.

395 5.1. Classification Accuracy Achieved on the Client Side

396 In this experiment, we first establish a local training baseline by measuring the
397 detection accuracies of the CNN architecture trained independently and in a cen-
398 tralized manner on the different partitions of the dataset, each of which resembles
399 the data captured by a separate and heterogeneous IoT client. For the CIC-IDS2018
400 dataset, the evaluation is conducted across five distributed clients. Table 6 presents
401 the corresponding results. The table shows that the model demonstrates robust
402 performance in terms of detecting various IoT attacks across multiple clients,
403 achieving accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score values of 100.00% for benign
404 traffic across all clients in the CIC-IDS2018 dataset. For the DDoS and other DoS
405 attack types, the model maintains high precision and recall levels, with an average
406 precision of 99.28% across the different attack types. However, the SlowHTTPTest
407 attack detection results show a minimum recall of 44.57% because these attacks
408 have low cardinality. Overall, the average accuracy of 99.28% achieved by the
409 model across diverse clients and attack types underscores its effectiveness for de-
410 tecting DDoS attacks in IoT environments. In client-side evaluations, it achieves
411 an average accuracy of 99.28%, a precision of 98.05%, a recall of 97.86%, and an
412 F1 score of 96.54%.

413 For the CIC-DDoS2019 dataset, we report the per-class performance achieved
414 across 12 DDoS attack types and benign traffic. As shown in Table 7, our client-
415 side evaluation yields an overall accuracy of 95.85%. Benign traffic is classified
416 with 98.10% accuracy, whereas the average accuracy attained for the DDoS attack
417 classes is 95.60%. Across those attack categories, the model attains a mean
418 precision level of 95.47%, a mean recall of 95.40%, and a mean F1 score of
419 95.50%.

420 For the BoT-IoT dataset, the results in Table 8 describe the classification per-
421 formance metrics achieved in the IoT DDoS attack detection scenarios. The results
422 demonstrate that most metrics reach values that are close to or equal to 100%. In
423 particular, the models achieve perfect or almost perfect scores for the *Benign* and
424 *Reconn* classes across all the metrics and clients, indicating their robustness and
425 reliability in terms of detecting these types of traffic. The *DDoS* and *Theft* classes
426 also exhibit high accuracy levels, consistently yielding scores $> 99.00\%$ for most
427 metrics, underscoring the effectiveness of the proposed model in identifying these
428 attacks. Even the *Scan* class—which is often considered more challenging—provides
429 excellent performance, with a classification accuracy of approximately 98%. Over-
430 all, the client-side evaluation of the model demonstrates an average accuracy of
431 99.20%, a precision of 99.70%, a recall of 99.85%, and an F1 score of 99.58%.

Table 6: Client-side evaluation results obtained on the CIC-IDS2018 dataset.

Class	Metric	Client accuracy [%]				
		IoT1	IoT2	IoT3	IoT4	IoT5
Benign	Precision	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	Recall	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	F1 score	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
DDoS attack–HOIC	Precision	97.12	97.23	97.14	97.18	97.34
	Recall	97.59	97.36	98.23	99.49	98.16
	F1 score	97.86	97.66	97.09	98.12	98.54
DDoS attack–LOIC-UDP	Precision	78.03	76.38	77.98	74.86	74.22
	Recall	87.20	89.10	84.18	85.00	87.00
	F1 score	83.34	84.48	84.08	84.80	84.00
DDoS attack–LOIC-HTTP	Precision	92.26	92.22	94.86	94.59	94.93
	Recall	98.21	99.87	98.49	98.99	98.62
	F1 score	95.12	95.10	96.91	96.87	96.93
DoS attack–GoldenEye	Precision	95.66	95.09	98.80	98.81	98.02
	Recall	98.21	99.02	99.87	99.49	99.99
	F1 score	96.04	97.64	99.13	99.81	99.64
DoS attack–Hulk	Precision	97.07	98.42	98.08	98.76	98.74
	Recall	99.27	98.82	99.41	98.51	99.36
	F1 score	98.19	99.85	99.30	99.87	99.15
DoS attack–SlowHTTPTest	Precision	77.11	67.48	68.82	78.37	79.02
	Recall	44.57	44.46	44.41	44.87	44.05
	F1 score	61.13	61.81	61.64	61.51	61.64
DoS attack–Slowloris	Precision	82.11	89.48	79.62	84.37	82.02
	Recall	77.40	75.62	76.49	76.98	76.50
	F1 score	88.07	85.42	86.08	86.64	86.32
Avg. accuracy		99.28				

432 For the CIC-IoT2023 dataset, which includes eight DDoS attack types and benign
433 traffic, the client-side evaluation yields an overall accuracy of 96.95% (Table
434 9). Benign samples are detected with 97.50% accuracy on average, whereas the
435 average accuracy attained for the IoT attack types is 96.80%. Across these attack
436 categories, the mean precision is 96.70%, the mean recall is 96.60%, and the mean
437 F1 score is 96.65%.

438 5.2. Comparison with Centralized with Federated Learning Models

439 In this experiment, we compare the accuracy of the proposed FELACS ap-
440 proach with those of centralized standalone models and FL-based aggregation
441 strategies, including random selection (Ruan et al., 2021; Ginanjar et al., 2025),
442 FedAvg (McMahan et al., 2017), FedProx (Li et al., 2020b), and FedMCCS (Ab-
443 dulRahman et al., 2020).

Table 7: Client-side evaluation results obtained on the CIC-DDoS2019 dataset.

Class	Metric	Client accuracy [%]				
		IoT1	IoT2	IoT3	IoT4	IoT5
Benign	Precision	98.98	99.08	98.85	98.75	98.72
	Recall	99.60	99.55	99.34	99.73	99.86
	F1 score	99.29	99.31	99.09	99.24	99.29
DNS	Precision	71.75	80.00	75.95	73.41	74.09
	Recall	67.65	76.33	75.16	78.87	79.67
	F1 score	69.86	78.93	73.85	74.81	76.98
SNMP	Precision	83.64	69.20	65.72	78.94	73.88
	Recall	86.28	74.71	63.55	75.14	74.61
	F1 score	85.70	77.85	62.59	76.05	74.15
LDAP	Precision	51.75	65.37	73.15	69.98	67.27
	Recall	52.28	71.28	86.41	90.25	65.53
	F1 score	56.83	68.03	79.34	81.16	66.26
MSSQL	Precision	89.22	85.16	93.15	92.69	88.67
	Recall	94.38	93.19	93.89	95.57	93.89
	F1 score	95.69	89.00	93.48	93.82	90.86
NTP	Precision	99.51	99.63	99.63	99.54	99.32
	Recall	99.05	99.44	99.35	99.06	99.34
	F1 score	99.28	99.54	99.49	99.37	99.33
NetBIOS	Precision	87.14	81.48	78.57	76.84	82.75
	Recall	70.94	82.30	73.18	72.72	80.67
	F1 score	81.36	85.69	75.78	74.78	81.54
SSDP	Precision	76.45	71.39	83.15	76.37	73.41
	Recall	82.28	73.23	93.89	73.72	71.29
	F1 score	79.52	72.27	88.20	74.82	72.37
Syn	Precision	98.50	97.25	97.63	98.62	95.24
	Recall	96.12	95.83	98.73	98.72	99.17
	F1 score	97.73	96.79	98.18	98.44	97.17
TFTP	Precision	100.00	99.69	99.98	100.00	99.93
	Recall	99.32	99.34	99.37	99.20	99.22
	F1 score	99.66	99.65	99.67	99.60	99.57
UDP	Precision	91.21	95.79	97.57	97.43	97.82
	Recall	97.34	93.87	95.23	95.83	95.82
	F1 score	94.05	94.65	96.40	96.62	96.89
WebDDoS	Precision	77.14	73.66	76.85	82.96	76.68
	Recall	69.43	71.28	74.18	95.57	74.34
	F1 score	73.63	72.28	75.27	88.82	75.57
Avg. accuracy			95.85			

Table 8: Client-side evaluation results obtained on the BoT-IoT dataset.

Class	Metric	Client accuracy [%]				
		IoT1	IoT2	IoT3	IoT4	IoT5
Benign	Accuracy	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	Precision	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	Recall	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	F-measure	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
DDoS	Accuracy	99.01	99.28	99.28	99.23	99.25
	Precision	99.31	99.49	99.63	98.77	99.10
	Recall	99.77	99.60	99.88	99.87	99.86
	F-measure	99.73	99.72	99.82	99.84	99.86
Reconn	Accuracy	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	Precision	99.73	98.59	99.70	99.60	99.29
	Recall	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	F-measure	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
Theft	Accuracy	99.00	99.00	99.00	99.00	99.00
	Precision	99.03	99.10	99.11	99.11	99.37
	Recall	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	F-measure	99.15	99.22	99.44	99.55	99.75
Scan	Accuracy	97.00	98.00	98.00	98.00	98.00
	Precision	98.00	98.08	98.15	98.08	98.15
	Recall	98.83	99.93	99.93	99.93	99.93
	F-measure	97.38	99.00	99.03	99.00	99.03
Avg. accuracy			99.20			

444 For the CIC-IDS2018 dataset, the results show that the proposed FELACS
445 method achieves $\approx 95.0\%$ accuracy, as shown in Figure 1a, outperforming the
446 other methods and even the centralized version. Similarly, for the CIC-DDoS2019
447 dataset, the results are shown in Figure 1b. Among the federated strategies,
448 FedMCCS and FELACS achieve the highest accuracies at $\approx 92.0\%$, also outperfor-
449 ming the centralized baseline. On the BoT-IoT dataset, as illustrated in Figure 1c,
450 FELACS also consistently outperforms the compared approaches, with $\approx 92.0\%$
451 accuracy. Considering the CIC-IoT2023 dataset, Figure 1d shows that, on a
452 more complex split, CL-sin reaches a top accuracy of approximately $\approx 99.0\%$;
453 FELACS has the best performance among the FL-based approaches, with an
454 average accuracy of $\approx 98.0\%$. Although the centralized model retains a small lead
455 in this scenario, FELACS matches or exceeds all other federated baselines.

456 The results obtained on the considered datasets confirm that our methodology
457 effectively adapts to changing traffic conditions, maintaining high accuracy levels
458 under all conditions, and is superior to other FL-based approaches, in some cases
459 surpassing the centralized version. This finding underscores two key points.
460 First, FL can approach or surpass the performance of centralized methods when

Table 9: Client-side evaluation results obtained on the CIC-IoT2023 dataset.

Class	Metric	Client accuracy [%]				
		IoT1	IoT2	IoT3	IoT4	IoT5
Benign	Precision	92.43	95.48	93.32	94.57	94.06
	Recall	95.75	97.24	96.22	97.87	98.23
	F1 score	93.08	93.20	93.20	93.20	93.20
BruteForce	Precision	97.57	95.89	96.94	94.87	94.87
	Recall	91.83	95.68	93.72	95.68	95.68
	F1 score	95.32	95.40	95.34	94.64	94.96
DDoS	Precision	99.67	97.64	98.39	98.74	99.82
	Recall	99.94	98.30	98.92	97.34	97.07
	F1 score	99.55	99.54	98.02	98.90	97.48
DoS	Precision	97.56	95.47	89.43	94.23	95.92
	Recall	87.57	89.66	87.76	93.64	96.04
	F1 score	94.70	93.68	89.86	92.72	95.99
Mirai	Precision	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	Recall	99.45	99.78	99.00	99.92	99.32
	F1 score	99.78	99.89	99.58	99.98	99.74
Recon	Precision	98.95	98.00	97.62	96.89	97.70
	Recall	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	99.74
	F1 score	99.08	99.01	98.76	98.46	98.68
Spoofing	Precision	83.79	83.80	83.00	83.00	83.00
	Recall	97.88	97.00	97.00	97.00	96.00
	F1 score	89.90	89.34	89.20	89.32	89.67
Web	Precision	74.64	89.00	78.27	76.66	74.64
	Recall	79.69	72.62	78.68	80.70	81.71
	F1 score	76.66	79.69	78.68	68.68	77.34
Avg. accuracy			98.86			

461 heterogeneity is properly managed. Second, by dynamically prioritizing clients
 462 with the most informative data under resource constraints, FELACS injects higher-
 463 quality updates into each aggregation step, increasing the accuracy of the global
 464 model without sacrificing privacy or incurring centralization overhead. As a
 465 consequence, we believe that the proposed methodology is able to adapt to modern
 466 IoT networks under a variety of network conditions.

467 5.3. Impact of the Number of Clients on Global Accuracy

468 In this section, we evaluate the accuracy achieved by the proposed method
 469 when varying the number of clients. Table 10 shows the average accuracy attained
 470 by the global model over 50 communication rounds as we vary the number of par-
 471 ticipating clients (10, 25, and 50) on four benchmarks. Across all the datasets, both
 472 FELACS+CNN and FELACS+VGG16 consistently outperform FedAvg, FedProx,

Figure 1: Accuracies achieved by various aggregation strategies and centralized standalone models on the considered datasets. It is possible to observe how the proposed FELACS method achieves the highest accuracy among the tested FL-based techniques, in some cases surpassing the centralized version (*CL-sin*).

473 FedMCCS, and random selection, with the VGG16 variant achieving the highest
 474 accuracy in every setting. In particular, on CIC-IDS2018, FELACS+CNN attains
 475 98.20%, 99.80%, and 99.40% accuracy values with 10, 25, and 50 clients, respec-
 476 tively, whereas FELACS+VGG16 further improves the performance to 98.50%,
 477 99.90%, and 99.60%—up to 1.40% higher than the metrics of the best baseline
 478 (FedProx). On CIC-DDoS2019, FELACS+CNN achieves 93.00%, 94.00%, and
 479 94.50% accuracy values, whereas FELACS+VGG16 reaches 93.50%, 94.50%, and
 480 95.00% accuracy values, exceeding those of FedProx by up to 1.40%. On BoT-IoT,
 481 the accuracies increase from 97.10%, 97.90%, and 98.30% for FELACS+CNN to
 482 97.40%, 98.10%, and 98.50% with FELACS+VGG16, surpassing the results of
 483 FedProx by as much as 1.40%. Finally, on CIC-IoT2023, FELACS+CNN delivers
 484 accuracies of 95.20%, 95.80%, and 96.00%, and FELACS+VGG16 reaches values
 485 95.50%, 96.10%, and 96.30%, outperforming all the baselines by 0.60 — —1.00%.

Table 10: Impact of the number of clients on the accuracy of the global model.

Algorithm	CIC-IDS2018			CIC-DDoS2019			BoT-IoT			CIC-IoT2023		
	10	25	50	10	25	50	10	25	50	10	25	50
FedAvg	97.00	97.80	98.20	91.80	92.40	93.00	96.80	97.60	98.00	94.20	94.80	95.10
FedProx	97.10	97.90	98.30	92.30	93.00	93.60	96.90	97.70	98.10	94.50	95.10	95.40
Random	96.80	97.50	97.90	91.20	91.80	92.40	96.60	97.30	97.80	93.80	94.30	94.60
FedMCCS	93.92	94.06	94.26	90.10	90.70	91.20	93.12	93.86	94.88	92.50	93.00	93.40
FELACS+CNN	98.20	99.80	99.40	93.00	94.00	94.50	97.10	97.90	98.30	95.20	95.80	96.00
FELACS+VGG16	98.50	99.90	99.60	93.50	94.50	95.00	97.40	98.10	98.50	95.50	96.10	96.30

486 The results produced with different numbers of clients confirm two key find-
487 ings. First, enlarging the client population improves the performance of the global
488 model by increasing the diversity of the samples. Second, integrating a deeper
489 VGG16 backbone with FELACS yields additional accuracy gains over the CNN
490 baseline, demonstrating robust and high-quality aggregated updates even under
491 severe non-IID conditions. As the client pool further expands, the gains decrease:
492 selecting up to 100 clients yields only marginal accuracy improvements over the
493 results obtained using fewer participants. Although a larger cohort can capture
494 more diverse data, this advantage plateaus beyond a certain point. Moreover, in-
495 tegrating VGG16, which has a substantially larger parameter count and a deeper
496 architecture, increases the computational and communication burdens imposed on
497 resource-constrained edge devices and IoT nodes. In our experiments, selecting
498 approximately 25 clients strikes the best balance between global accuracy and
499 system efficiency, providing sufficient data diversity to avoid both underfitting and
500 overfitting without incurring the excessive training time, memory usage, and band-
501 width demands that arise when many devices must process or transmit updates
502 for a heavyweight model such as VGG16. This underscores the importance of
503 a strategic client selection strategy that jointly considers model complexity and
504 limited edge resources.

505 5.4. Classification Results

506 The FL model classification results obtained on the CIC-IDS2018 dataset when
507 our FELACS client selection strategy is applied are presented in Figure 2a. The per-
508 formance metrics produced across 100 communication rounds demonstrate that the
509 proposed FELACS approach outperforms the FedAvg, FedProx, FedMCCS, and
510 Random methods, achieving higher accuracy throughout all the training rounds.
511 Similarly, Figure 2b presents the accuracy curves obtained for CIC-DDoS2019.
512 The figure shows that FELACS consistently outperforms the baselines, exceeding

Figure 2: Detection accuracies attained over 100 communication rounds on the considered datasets with different client selection strategies. The proposed FELACS approach outperforms the other FL-based methods.

513 98.8% accuracy and maintaining stable performance. Figure 2c illustrates the
 514 accuracy achieved on the BoT-IoT dataset. The accuracy curves converge toward
 515 values near 100%, with the FELACS method reaching the highest final accuracy.
 516 On the CIC-IoT2023 dataset (Figure 2d), FELACS achieves over 98% accuracy by
 517 round 20 while also attaining the highest steady-state accuracy of approximately
 518 99.5%.

519 5.5. Communication Overhead

520 In this section, we evaluate the number of communication rounds needed to
 521 achieve convergence. In particular, Table 11 illustrates the numbers of rounds
 522 needed to reach 90% and 95% accuracy under both IID and non-IID splits for all

Table 11: Numbers of communication rounds required to reach 95% and 90% accuracy (IID / non-IID) on the considered datasets.

Approach	CIC-IDS2018		CIC-DDoS2019		BoT-IoT		CIC-IoT2023	
	ToA@95	ToA@90	ToA@95	ToA@90	ToA@95	ToA@90	ToA@95	ToA@90
FedAvg	38/43	32/36	50/58	42/50	46/54	40/46	44/52	36/44
FedProx	36/40	30/34	48/54	40/46	44/50	38/43	42/48	35/40
Random	50/58	42/48	65/75	56/64	60/68	52/56	58/68	50/56
FedMCCS	34/38	28/32	46/52	38/44	42/48	36/40	40/46	34/38
FELACS+CNN	30/35	25/28	40/46	32/38	38/45	32/38	36/42	30/34
FELACS+VGG16	28/32	23/26	38/44	30/36	36/43	30/36	34/40	28/32

523 four datasets. As expected, heterogeneous distributions incur higher communica-
524 tion costs: each method requires several more rounds in the non-IID setting than
525 in the IID setting. Traditional schemes such as FedAvg and FedProx generally
526 converge in the mid-30s to mid-40s (rounds) when aiming for 90% accuracy and
527 the high-30s to mid-50s for 95%. Random selection is the least efficient approach,
528 often demanding upward of 60 rounds to reach the same thresholds under skewed
529 data. In contrast, the FELACS approaches substantially reduce this overhead,
530 achieving both targets in the low-30s to low-40s even when the data are highly
531 imbalanced. These results demonstrate that by prioritizing clients whose updates
532 carry maximal utility while respecting resource constraints, FL can preserve the
533 fidelity of a model with far fewer communication exchanges, which is an essential
534 property for real-time IoT deployments.

535 5.6. Model Convergence Time Analysis

536 In this section, we evaluate the convergence times required by the considered
537 approaches. Table 12 provides a comparative analysis of the temporal efficiency
538 levels of various FL methods across 100 communication rounds on the examined
539 datasets. The results indicate that the proposed FELACS method has better perfor-
540 mance than the existing approaches do, achieving lower average communication
541 times and requiring fewer rounds for convergence. These findings show the po-
542 tential of FELACS to reduce the imposed communication overhead and enhance
543 the overall efficiency of FL in IoT environments, positioning it as a promising
544 approach for real-world applications. However, when applying FELACS to the
545 deeper VGG16 architecture, the increased parameter count and layer depth of
546 this network introduce significant communication and computational overhead for
547 resource-constrained IoT and edge devices. In our experiments, FELACS+VGG16
548 yields the highest accuracy but requires substantially more bandwidth per round

Table 12: Per-round time (minutes) required by different FL client selection methods for four datasets.

Method	CIC-IDS2018		CIC-DDoS2019		BoT-IoT		CIC-IoT2023	
	Mean	Std	Mean	Std	Mean	Std	Mean	Std
FedAvg	5.45	0.32	6.00	0.35	5.12	0.28	5.00	0.30
FedProx	<u>5.20</u>	<u>0.25</u>	<u>5.80</u>	<u>0.30</u>	<u>4.98</u>	<u>0.22</u>	<u>4.80</u>	<u>0.24</u>
Random	6.30	0.50	7.00	0.55	6.05	0.45	6.10	0.48
FedMCCS	9.20	0.87	9.80	1.00	8.76	0.79	9.00	0.85
FELACS+CNN	4.82	0.20	5.30	0.22	4.65	0.18	4.50	0.16
FELACS+VGG16	9.50	0.86	11.80	1.35	8.20	0.56	9.00	0.98

549 than does FELACS+CNN. To mitigate this overhead in real-world deployments, it
550 may be possible to use model compression techniques, such as 8-bit quantization
551 and pruning, to reduce payload sizes and computational loads, thereby preserving
552 the convergence gains provided by FELACS+VGG16 while satisfying IoT/edge
553 resource constraints.

554 We also theoretically analyze the convergence of the proposed approach by
555 considering the demonstration presented in (Li and Lyu, 2023), which states that
556 sequential FL converges on heterogeneous data at an $O(1/T)$ rate for strongly
557 convex objectives, provided that each client has a positive probability of being
558 selected in each round. Moreover, the works of (Cho et al., 2020; Wang and Ji,
559 2022) demonstrated the convergence of client selection schemes with bounded
560 gradient estimation. In this context, the multicriteria optimization scheme of
561 FELACS ensures that every client retains a strictly positive selection probability
562 and keeps the gradient estimation variance bounded. Moreover, the federated
563 multiobjective learning framework (Yang et al., 2023; Vardhan et al., 2025) extends
564 identical guarantees to multigradient aggregation scenarios. FELACS satisfies all
565 core assumptions of these convergence theories and therefore exhibits the predicted
566 convergence behavior in our IoT DDoS detection experiments.

567 5.7. Sensitivity Analysis

568 We assess the robustness of the proposed approach by varying each weight (α ,
569 β , γ , δ) by $\pm 20\%$ around its default value and then measure the detection accuracy
570 and F1 score values achieved on the CIC-IDS2018, CIC-DDoS2019, BoT-IoT, and
571 CIC-IoT2023 datasets. Across all the perturbations and datasets, the maximum
572 accuracy and F1 score deviations remain within $\pm 5\%$. These findings confirm that
573 the importance scoring function of our proposed FELACS approach tolerates mod-
574 erate hyperparameter shifts without significant performance losses, reducing the

575 burden of fine-tuning in real-world federated IoT deployments. The demonstrated
576 robustness suggests that practitioners can confidently apply our method under
577 various device conditions and network characteristics with minimal recalibration.

578 **6. Conclusion**

579 In this paper, we propose FELACS, an adaptive client selection approach for
580 detecting IoT DDoS attacks in FL scenarios. Our approach considers multiobjec-
581 tive optimization, considering both the diversity and importance of client data, as
582 well as the real-time performance of client devices. In contrast with the existing
583 methods in the literature, our approach integrates a multiobjective optimization
584 framework that evaluates key factors, including data entropy, variance, power con-
585 sumption, and latency, for each client. This comprehensive approach ensures an
586 effective and balanced client selection process during FL, mitigating client drift by
587 favoring the clients with the most representative data and sufficient computational
588 resources.

589 We validate the developed method on four publicly available datasets and
590 demonstrate that our algorithm achieves better classification accuracy than that
591 of a nonfederated model and does so in fewer communication rounds. Moreover,
592 we evaluate the performance of the method in comparison with that of FedAvg,
593 FedProx, FedMCCS, and random client selection, with our approach achieving
594 better accuracy and faster convergence than those of the existing methods in the
595 literature. Future works will focus on developing robust, scalable, and interpretable
596 models using federated transfer learning to enhance the DDoS attack detection
597 process in IoT environments.

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609 **References**

- 610 AbdulRahman, S., Tout, H., Mourad, A., Talhi, C., 2020. FedMCCS: Multicriteria
611 client selection model for optimal IoT federated learning. *IEEE Internet of
612 Things Journal* 8, 4723–4735.
- 613 Agostinello, D., Genovese, A., Piuri, V., 2023. Anomaly-based intrusion detection
614 system for DDoS attack with deep learning techniques, in: *Proc. of SECRIPT*,
615 pp. 267–275.
- 616 Aktar, S., Nur, A.Y., 2023. Towards DDoS attack detection using deep learning
617 approach. *Computers & Security* 129, 103251.
- 618 Ami, D.B., Cohen, K., Zhao, Q., 2025. Client selection for generalization in
619 accelerated federated learning: A multi-armed bandit approach. *IEEE Access*
620 13, 33697–33713.
- 621 Anand, R., Aggarwal, D., Kumar, V., 2017. A comparative analysis of optimization
622 solvers. *Journal of Statistics and Management Systems* 20, 623–635.
- 623 Anley, M.B., Genovese, A., Agostinello, D., Piuri, V., 2024. Robust DDoS attack
624 detection with adaptive transfer learning. *Computers & Security* 144, 103962.
- 625 Anley, M.B., Genovese, A., Piuri, V., 2025. TransferEdge: Transfer learning
626 approach to detect evolving DDoS threats in Edge-IIoT, in: *Proc. of RTSI*, pp.
627 1–6.
- 628 Beutel, D.J., Topal, T., Mathur, A., Qiu, X., Fernandez-Marques, J., Gao, Y., Sani,
629 L., Li, K.H., Parcollet, T., de Gusmão, P.P.B., et al., 2020. Flower: A friendly
630 federated learning research framework, in: *arXiv:2007.14390*, pp. 1–15.
- 631 Bonawitz, K.A., Eichner, H., Grieskamp, W., Huba, D., Ingerman, A., Ivanov,
632 V., Kiddon, C., Konečný, J., Mazzocchi, S., McMahan, B., Overveldt, T.V.,
633 Petrou, D., Ramage, D., Roselander, J., 2019. Towards federated learning at
634 scale: System design, in: *Proc. of SysML*, pp. 1–15.
- 635 Cho, Y.J., Wang, J., Joshi, G., 2020. Client selection in federated learning: Conver-
636 gence analysis and power-of-choice selection strategies, in: *arXiv:2010.01243*,
637 pp. 1–22.

- 638 Elfaki, M.A., Alshahrani, H.M., Mahmood, K., Alabdan, R., Alymani, M., Al-
639 shahrani, H., Motwakel, A., Alneil, A.A., 2023. Metaheuristics algorithm-based
640 minimization of communication costs in federated learning. *IEEE Access* 11,
641 81310–81317.
- 642 Feng, J., Liu, L., Pei, Q., Li, K., 2021. Min-max cost optimization for efficient
643 hierarchical federated learning in wireless edge networks. *IEEE Transactions*
644 *on Parallel and Distributed Systems* 33, 2687–2700.
- 645 Fotse, Y.S.N., Tchendji, V.K., Velempini, M., 2024. Federated learning based
646 DDoS attacks detection in large scale software-defined network. *IEEE Trans.*
647 *on Computers* 74, 101–115.
- 648 Fu, L., Zhang, H., Gao, G., Zhang, M., Liu, X., 2023. Client selection in federated
649 learning: Principles, challenges, and opportunities. *IEEE Internet of Things*
650 *Journal* 10, 21811–21819.
- 651 Ginanjar, A., Li, X., Singh, P., Hua, W., 2025. Random client selection on
652 contrastive federated learning for tabular data, in: *arXiv:2505.10759*, pp. 1–5.
- 653 Gümüşbaş, D., Yıldırım, T., Genovese, A., Scotti, F., 2021. A comprehensive
654 survey of databases and deep learning methods for cybersecurity and intrusion
655 detection systems. *IEEE Systems Journal* 15, 1717–1731.
- 656 Hsu, T.M.H., Qi, H., Brown, M., 2019. Measuring the effects of non-identical data
657 distribution for federated visual classification, in: *arXiv:1909.06335*, pp. 1–5.
- 658 Hu, Z., Shaloudegi, K., Zhang, G., Yu, Y., 2022. Federated learning meets multi-
659 objective optimization. *IEEE Trans. on Network Science and Engineering* 9,
660 2039–2051.
- 661 Kairouz, P., McMahan, H.B., Avent, B., Bellet, A., Bennis, M., Bhagoji, A.N.,
662 Bonawitz, K., Charles, Z., Cormode, G., Cummings, R., et al., 2021. Advances
663 and open problems in federated learning. *Foundations and trends® in machine*
664 *learning* 14, 1–210.
- 665 Koroniotis, N., Moustafa, N., Sitnikova, E., Turnbull, B., 2019. Towards the
666 development of realistic botnet dataset in the internet of things for network
667 forensic analytics: BoT-IoT dataset. *Future Generation Computer Systems* 100,
668 779–796.

- 669 Li, B., Wu, Y., Song, J., Lu, R., Li, T., Zhao, L., 2020a. DeepFed: Federated
670 deep learning for intrusion detection in industrial cyber-physical systems. *IEEE*
671 *Transactions on Industrial Informatics* 17, 5615–5624.
- 672 Li, J., Chen, T., Teng, S., 2024. A comprehensive survey on client selection
673 strategies in federated learning. *Computer Networks* 251, 1–15.
- 674 Li, J., Zhang, Z., Li, Y., Guo, X., Li, H., 2021. FIDS: Detecting DDoS through
675 federated learning based method, in: *Proc. of TrustCom*, pp. 856–862.
- 676 Li, T., Sahu, A.K., Zaheer, M., Sanjabi, M., Talwalkar, A., Smith, V., 2020b.
677 Federated optimization in heterogeneous networks. *Proc. of Machine Learning*
678 *and Systems* 2, 429–450.
- 679 Li, Y., Lyu, X., 2023. Convergence analysis of sequential federated learning on
680 heterogeneous data, in: *Proc. of NIPS*, pp. 56700–56755.
- 681 Lim, W.Y.B., Luong, N.C., Hoang, D.T., Jiao, Y., Liang, Y.C., Yang, Q., Niyato, D.,
682 Miao, C., 2020. Federated learning in mobile edge networks: A comprehensive
683 survey. *IEEE communications surveys & tutorials* 22, 2031–2063.
- 684 Ma, X., Zhu, J., Lin, Z., Chen, S., Qin, Y., 2022. A state-of-the-art survey
685 on solving non-IID data in federated learning. *Future Generation Computer*
686 *Systems* 135, 244–258.
- 687 Maciel, F., De Souza, A.M., Bittencourt, L.F., Villas, L.A., 2023. Resource aware
688 client selection for federated learning in IoT scenarios, in: *Proc. of DCOSS-IoT*,
689 pp. 1–8.
- 690 Mazid, A., Kirmani, S., Manaullah, Yadav, M., 2025. FL-IDPP: A federated
691 learning based intrusion detection approach with privacy preservation. *Trans.*
692 *on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies* 36, e70039.
- 693 McMahan, B., Moore, E., Ramage, D., Hampson, S., y Arcas, B.A., 2017.
694 Communication-efficient learning of deep networks from decentralized data,
695 in: *Artificial Intelligence and Statistics*, pp. 1273–1282.
- 696 Neto, E.C.P., Dadkhah, S., Ferreira, R., Zohourian, A., Lu, R., Ghorbani, A.A.,
697 2023. CICIoT2023: A real-time dataset and benchmark for large-scale attacks
698 in IoT environment.

- 699 Nguyen, Q.H., Hore, S., Shah, A., Le, T., Bastian, N.D., 2025. FedNIDS: A federated learning framework for packet-based network intrusion detection system. Digital Threats: Research and Practice 6, 1–23.
- 700
701
- 702 Nishio, T., Yonetani, R., 2019. Client selection for federated learning with heterogeneous resources in mobile edge, in: Proc. of ICC, pp. 1–7.
- 703
- 704 Olanrewaju-George, B., Pranggono, B., 2025. Federated learning-based intrusion detection system for the internet of things using unsupervised and supervised deep learning models. Cyber Security and Applications 3, 100068.
- 705
706
- 707 Pakmehr, A., Aßmuth, A., Taheri, N., Ghaffari, A., 2024. Ddos attack detection techniques in IoT networks: a survey. Cluster Computing 27, 14637–14668.
- 708
- 709 Puchinger, J., Raidl, G.R., Pferschy, U., 2010. The multidimensional knapsack problem: Structure and algorithms. INFORMS Journal on Computing 22, 250–265.
- 710
711
- 712 Rahmati, M., 2025. Federated learning-driven cybersecurity framework for IoT networks with privacy-preserving and real-time threat detection capabilities, in: arXiv:2502.10599, pp. 1–16.
- 713
714
- 715 Roy, S., Li, J., Bai, Y., 2023. Federated learning-based intrusion detection system for IoT environments with locally adapted model, in: Proc. of CSCloud/EdgeCom, pp. 203–209.
- 716
717
- 718 Ruan, Y., Zhang, X., Liang, S.C., Joe-Wong, C., 2021. Towards flexible device participation in federated learning, in: Proc. of ICAIS, PMLR. pp. 3403–3411.
- 719
- 720 Ruzafa-Alcázar, P., Fernández-Saura, P., Mármol-Campos, E., González-Vidal, A., Hernández-Ramos, J.L., Bernal-Bernabe, J., Skarmeta, A.F., 2021. Intrusion detection based on privacy-preserving federated learning for the industrial IoT. IEEE Trans. on Industrial Informatics 19, 1145–1154.
- 721
722
723
- 724 Seo, S., Lee, J., Ko, H., Pack, S., 2022. Performance-aware client and quantization level selection algorithm for fast federated learning, in: Proc. of WCNC, pp. 1892–1897.
- 725
726
- 727 Sharafaldin, I., Lashkari, A.H., Ghorbani, A.A., 2018. Toward generating a new intrusion detection dataset and intrusion traffic characterization. ICISSp 1, 108–116.
- 728
729

- 730 Sharafaldin, I., Lashkari, A.H., Hakak, S., Ghorbani, A.A., 2019. Developing
731 realistic distributed denial of service (DDoS) attack dataset and taxonomy, in:
732 Proc. of ICCST, pp. 1–8.
- 733 Sun, S., Sharma, P., Nwodo, K., Stavrou, A., Wang, H., 2024. FedMADE: Robust
734 federated learning for intrusion detection in IoT networks using a dynamic
735 aggregation method, in: Proc. of ICIS, pp. 286–306.
- 736 Tahir, M., Mawla, T., Awaysheh, F., Alawadi, S., Gupta, M., Ali, M.I., 2025.
737 SecureFedPROM: A zero-trust federated learning approach with multi-criteria
738 client selection. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications* 43, 2025–
739 2041.
- 740 Vardhan, H., Yu, X., Rosing, T., Mazumdar, A., 2025. Client selection in federated
741 learning with data heterogeneity and network latencies, in: arXiv:2504.01921,
742 pp. 1–23.
- 743 Wang, H., Yurochkin, M., Sun, Y., Papailiopoulos, D.S., Khazaeni, Y., 2020.
744 Federated learning with matched averaging, in: Proc. of ICLR, pp. 1–16.
- 745 Wang, S., Ji, M., 2022. A unified analysis of federated learning with arbitrary
746 client participation, in: Proc. of NIPS, pp. 19124–19137.
- 747 Wu, H., Tang, X., Zhang, Y.J.A., Gao, L., 2023. Incentive mechanism for federated
748 learning with random client selection. *IEEE Trans. on Network Science and
749 Engineering* 11, 1922–1933.
- 750 Yang, H., Liu, Z., Liu, J., Dong, C., Momma, M., 2023. Federated multi-objective
751 learning. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 36, 39602–39625.
- 752 Zhang, J., Li, S., Wang, C., 2024. Utility aware optimal data selection for differ-
753 entially private federated learning in IoV. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal* 11,
754 33326–33336.
- 755 Zhao, Y., Li, M., Lai, L., Suda, N., Civin, D., Chandra, V., 2018. Federated
756 learning with non-IID data, in: arXiv:1806.00582, pp. 1–12.